

Data associated with the publication: Deer slow down litter decomposition by reducing litter quality in a temperate forest by Chollet et al. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1101/690032>

The files correspond to decomposition rate after one year in the temperate forest of Haida Gwaii (BC, Canada) in three herbivory treatment (absent, intermediate, severe).

Files description:

1) Closs_Nloss_Litter-Composition.xlsx

Composition: origin of the litter in the litterbag.

Place decomposition: location of decomposition during one year

2) Closs_Nloss_Spruce-Feces.xlsx

Composition: origin of the litter in the litterbag. F= feces, FS_F= feces+spruce, T=spruce alone.

Place decomposition: location of decomposition during one year